

THE VARIOUS APPROACHES OF GIVING A SPEECH IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE.

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Abstract: to become competent in communication, to learn how to interact with people and to speak expressively and fluently in public.

Keywords: Public speaking, techniques, audience, lecture, talks

Annotatsiya: muloqotda tajribali bo'lish, odamlar bilan qanday munosabatda bo'lishni va omma oldida ifodali va ravon gapirishni o'rganish.

Kalit so'zlar: Omma oldida nutq, texnika, auditoriya, ma'ruza, muloqot

Аннотация: статья компетентным в общении, научиться взаимодействовать с людьми и выразительно и бегло говорить на публике.

Ключевые слова: Публичное выступление, техники, аудитория, лекция, переговоры

Public speaking, also known as a lecture or speech, traditionally means the act of speaking face-to-face with a live audience. Public speaking is used for a variety of purposes, but is often a mixture of teaching, persuasion, or entertainment. Each of them is based on a slightly different approach and technique. Today, the art of public speaking has been transformed by new technologies such as video conferencing, multimedia presentations and other non-traditional forms, but the basic elements remain the same. Public speaking is when you stand before an audience and deliver a speech on a topic. This could be at a formal or an informal occasion. For many people, speaking in front of a large audience is a daunting task so it is quite natural to become very nervous. As public speaking has become a serious career option, many people are enrolling for public speaking classes where they are taught skills and techniques to speak well and speak effectively before a gathering. However, to become a good speaker students should know some tips of public speaking.

1. Speaking to inform.

When you give a speech before an audience to impart information on a particular topic or issue, it is said to be an informative speech. Business presentations, seminars in colleges, class presentations in schools are some examples of informative speeches

A person preparing for an informative speech has to research the subject or topic very well. It should be short and precise because long informative speeches (e.g. lectures) can easily bore your audience. The success of an informative speech will depend on how much the audience could understand from the speech..

2. Speaking to Persuade.

In persuasive presentations, you attempt to alter your audience's perception of a concept, a product, a person, etc. These speeches seek to persuade listeners and alter their perspectives in favor of or against the topic. Given that you can be dealing with a group of individuals whose opinions differ greatly from your own, this can be a challenging undertaking. The most

crucial thing to remember here is that you must talk with enthusiasm if you wish to affect other people's opinions and beliefs. But you must keep in mind that you are not there to fight; as a result, you must speak politely and without offending anyone. Persuasive speeches are often given by sales and marketing people to attract interest in their products. They are also used to influence political and religious views.

3. Speaking to Actuate.

A higher level of persuasive speaking is speaking to act. The speaker in this instance goes above and beyond persuasion and convincing. The goal is to persuade them to act—to be sufficiently moved. Speaking at this level is effective. Very few persons have mastered the art of persuasion to the extent that they could so powerfully persuade others to take action.

Even though they may be presented, facts and data are often not the focus of an actuating speech. The speaker wants to emotionally stir his audience so that they will firmly adopt his thought, his beliefs, and his logic as their own and figuratively take up the cross and bear his burden. Sometimes, listeners may be so moved by what they hear that they commit to the cause even more firmly than the person who first asked them to do so! This represents the apex of public speaking and persuasive speech.

4. Speaking to Entertain.

Another type of public speaking is ceremonial speaking, which is typically delivered at weddings, funerals, graduation celebrations, retirement parties, etc. A personal touch is a crucial component in making these talks effective.

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